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Research Article

**A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY TO DETERMINE THE
OCCURRENCE OF ACCIDENTAL POISONING OF
ETIOLOGICAL AGENTS IN CHILDREN**Dr Muhammad Younas Khan¹, Dr Kamranullah², Dr Abdul Wahab³¹Khyber Medical University, Peshawar, ^{2,3}POF hospital, Wah Cantt

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Abstract:

Objective: The aim of our study was to determine the occurrence of accidental poisoning of etiological agents in children.

Study Design: A cross sectional study.

Place and Duration: This study was conducted in Department of Pediatrics, POF hospital, Wah Cantt Pakistan for the duration of six months starting from March, 2020 to September, 2020.

Methodology: In our present study we included 220 patients of accidental poisoning age range is less than 12 years. We took an informed consent from the parents of the children to enter the children data in our study. Data was recorded in the study with respect to age and gender. Parents were interviewed in detail with respect to the name of offending chemical, and the route of entry of a substance was also made for the inquiry of drug medication. We sent container to the laboratory to identify toxic where the covering and wrapping of a material were available. We took samples from stomach and sent for analysis of disease. We categorized all the patients depending on the component involved in poisoning.

Results: We include 220 patients in our study. In which 105 patients (47.73%) age range between 0 to 6 years while 115 patients (52.27%) age range between 7 to 12 years. 6.67+2.39 years were their mean age. In the selected patients, large number of patients were females 125 (56.82%). The substance that was responsible for accidental poisoning were present in 54 patients having petroleum-based products (24.55%), 41 having insecticides (18.63%), 81 having pharmacological agents (36.82%) and 44 were those having acid/alkali (20%).

Conclusions: At the end of our study, we conclude that the most common substance in children for accidental poisoning is pharmacological agents. Such studies like ours can help to devise suggestions for the public education to control the morbidity and mortality of children.

Keywords: Acid/Alkali Ingestion, Pharmacological Agents, Accidental Poisoning in Children, Insecticides, Petroleum Based Products, Etiological Factor.

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INTRODUCTION:

Poisoning in children is quite common and is a significant cause of morbidity and mortality and fortunately most cases are preventable [1]. Poisoning is prevalent worldwide and no nation is immune to it, however the types of involved substance may vary in different populations because of a number of factors and ease of access. The ease of access of many substances involved in poisoning also depends on many factors like customs and social norms (kerosene oils and many other liquid poisoning substances are kept in empty soft drink bottles in Southeast Asia), economic and educational status of family etc. [2]. Mortality due to accidental poisoning is high in children especially those who are less than 4 years because children in this age group are not able to talk about the incidence and they are often picked up and diagnosed quite late [3,4]. A number of agents has been recognized as common substances involved in poisoning in children and adolescents. These are antipsychotic agents, antiepileptics, pain killers including paracetamol and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, antidepressants and sedatives.

Apart from these medicinal poisonings a number of other agents has also been commonly involved in accidental poisoning in children and these includes kerosene oil especially when it is contained in soft drink bottles, insecticides especially organo-phosphorous compounds, rat killing pills, bleach and caustics etc. Worldwide epidemiological researches on childhood poisoning are showing similar patterns being more common in less than 6-years of age children and among them boys are more involved than girls as they are more interested to explore the world as compared to girls and also more involved in outdoor activities. The incidence of accidental poisoning is especially high in boys [5,6]. The incidence of intentional poisoning done for suicidal purpose is more in adolescent females as compared to boys, the accidental poisoning done for homicidal purpose is not common in children [7]. The current study is done to determine the etiological agents of accidental poisoning in children as various local studies show a variable trend. This would help us to formulate recommendations for public education so that this preventable cause of childhood mortality and morbidity can be controlled [8,9].

METHODOLOGY:

This cross-sectional study was conducted in Department of Pediatrics, POF hospital, Wah Cantt

Pakistan for the duration of six months starting from March, 2020 to September, 2020. A sample size of 220 cases was determined with 95% confidence level, 4% margin of error and taking expected percentage of alkali/acid ingestion of 10% in children with accidental poisoning. The study population was sampled using nonprobability purposive sampling technique. Children presenting to the Emergency Room with age between 6 months to 12 years (both genders) with accidental poisoning were included in the study. According to WHO poisoning was defined as injury or destruction of the cells by the inhalation, ingestion, injection or absorption of a toxic substance. Two hundred and twenty children fulfilling the inclusion criteria, admitted in Department of Pediatrics, POF hospital, Wah Cantt were enrolled. Informed consent of the parents of children was taken. Demographic profile age, gender, was recorded.

Detailed interview of parents and children was done regarding name of the involved substance and about route of entry and timing. For recognition of poison container, its label and wrapper were taken. Samples from stomach were also taken where indicated and sent to hospital laboratory for analysis. Classification of cases was done according to offending agent involved. All cases were managed according to the departmental protocols. Etiological factors for accidental poisoning in children were recorded on a pre-designed proforma. The data was analyzed through SPSS version 16. Mean+SD was calculated for age. Frequency and percentage were calculated for categorical variable i.e., gender and etiological factors of poisoning in children i.e., pharmacological agents, petroleum-based products, acid/alkali ingestion and insecticides. Stratification for age and gender was done to control the effect modifiers. Post stratification chi-square test was applied. A p value < 0.05 was taken significant.

RESULTS:

A total of 220 cases fulfilling the inclusion criteria were enrolled to determine the frequency of etiological factors of accidental poisoning in children presenting to POF hospital, Wah Cantt. Demographics are given in Table 01 and 02. The substances responsible for accidental poisoning were pharmacological agents (36.82%, n=81), petroleum-based products (24.55%, n=54), acid/alkali (20%, n=44) and insecticides (18.63%, n=41).

Table No 01: Age Distribution

Age	Qty	%age
0-6 years	105	47.73%
7-12 years	115	52.27%
Total	220	100%

Table No 02: Gender Distribution

Gender	Qty	%age
Male	95	43.18%
Female	125	56.82%
Total	220	100%

Table No 03: Frequency of Etiological Agents of Accidental Poisoning in Children

Etiological agents	Qty	%age
Pharmacological agents	81	36.82%
Petroleum base products	54	24.55%
Acid/Alkali ingestion	44	20%
Insecticides	41	18.63%
Total	220	100%

Table No 04: Stratification for Etiological Agents of Accidental Poisoning in Children with Regards to Age

Etiological agents	Age (years)		P-value
	0-6	7-12	
Pharmacological agents (n=81)	41	40	0.51
Petroleum base products (n=54)	23	31	0.38
Acid/Alkali (n=44)	22	22	0.74
Insecticides (n=41)	19	22	0.84

Table No 05: Stratification for Etiological Agents of Accidental Poisoning in Children with Regards to Gender

Etiological agents	Gender		P-value
	Male	Female	
Pharmacological agents (n=81)	45	36	0.05
Petroleum base products (n=54)	22	32	0.68
Acid/Alkali (n=44)	22	22	0.01
Insecticides (n=41)	79	25	0.05

Stratification for etiological agents of accidental poisoning in children with regards to age and gender are presented in Table No. 4 & 5. It was observed that

there was no significant difference in the use of poisons with regards to age of the children however males were more likely to ingest pharmacological

agents ($p < 0.05$), acid/alkali ($p = 0.01$) and insecticides ($p < 0.05$) as compared to females.

DISCUSSION:

We planned this study with the view to determine the frequency of etiological agents of accidental poisoning in children as various local studies shown a marked variation in results thus indicating the need for further studies so that trends of etiological agents of poisoning can be followed. In a study conducted at Karachi accidental poisoning by various agents was recorded and kerosene oil poisoning (56%) was the commonest followed by insecticides (17.5%), pharmacological agents (16%) and acid/alkali ingestion (10%), the findings of this study are contrary to present research. A study conducted in northern India indicate that male is more prone to suffer from accidental poisoning and kerosene oil poisoning (27.9%) was the commonest substance followed by drugs (19.8%) and insecticides (11.7%). Many local, Indian and studies done in other parts of world also reveals male preponderance in childhood poisoning [10,11,12]. However few studies from Ankra and Trinidad are indicating female preponderance [13,14] and these findings are similar to our study. Although boys were more commonly affected in the under 5 age group, this was balanced by a higher number of adolescent girls. Insecticides in this study accounted for 18.63% cases. Kerosene is used as a cooking fuel in our country by low-income families and is stored in bottles usually within easy reach of children.

These are many a times stored in empty water bottles predisposing young children to accidentally consume them. Relative data has discovered that poisoning in developed world is usually with household substances but when we talk about developing countries, the patterns are somewhat different. Many toxic agents which should be out of reach of children are kept in houses where children can have easy access. Preventive measures should be taken to keep all these substances out of the reach of children. These agents should be contained in proper containers and at places where children can't have access. Proper awareness and health education of the community is also very important and that can be done by seminars, by newspapers and by electronic media. We are of the view that the frequency of etiological agents of accidental poisoning in children is different in different nations and the reason for this variation is customs, life style and educational status etc. However, our study can help us to formulate recommendations for the public education so that this preventable cause of childhood mortality and morbidity can be controlled.

CONCLUSION:

At the end of our study, we conclude that the most common substance in children for accidental poisoning is pharmacological agents. Such studies like ours can help to devise suggestions for the public education to control the morbidity and mortality of children.

REFERENCES:

1. Abbas SK, Tikmani SS, Siddiqui NT. Accidental poisoning in children. *J Pak Med Assoc JPMA* 2012; 62:331.
2. Manzar N, Saad SMA, Manzar B, Fatima SS. The study of etiological and demographic characteristics of acute household accidental poisoning in children a consecutive case series study from Pakistan. *BMC Pediatrics* 2014; 10: 28-30.
3. Randev S, Grover N, Sharma R, Sharma H. Acute poisoning in children: seven-year experience at a tertiary care hospital of north India. *Curr Pediatr Res* 2011; 15(1): 65-8.
4. Manzar N, Saad SMA, Manzar B, Fatima SS. The study of etiological and demographic characteristics of acute household accidental poisoning in children a consecutive case series study from Pakistan. *BMC Pediatrics* 2011; 10: 28-30
5. Aqeel M, Munir A, Khan A. Pattern and frequency of acute poisoning in children. *Pak J Med Sci* 2019; 25(3): 479-483)
6. Chatsantiprapa K, Chokkanapatik J, Pinpradit N. Host and environmental factors for exposure to poisons: A cross sectional study of preschool children in Thailand. *Inj Prev* 2018; 7: L 214-17.
7. Hon KL, Ho JK, Leung TH, Wong Y, Nelson EA, Fok TF. Review of children hospitalized for ingestion and poisoning at tertiary center. *Ann Acad Med Singapore* 2015; 34: 356-61.
8. Peden M, Oyegbite K, Ozanne-Smith J, et al., editors. *World Report on Child Injury Prevention* Geneva: World Health Organization;
9. Ahmed I, Ahmed E, Ahmed Z, Saeed A, Sabir S. Accidental poisoning in children: frequency and outcome of the cases at a military hospital. *PAFMJ* 2015; 4:221-4.)
10. Kohli U, Kuttiaat VS, Lodha R, Kabra SK. Profile of Childhood Poisoning at a Tertiary Care Centre in North India. *Indian J Pediatr* 2018; 75: 791-4.
11. Adejuyigbe EA, Onayade AA, Senbanjo IO, Oseni SE. Childhood poisoning at the Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospital, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. *Niger J Med* 2012; 11(4): 183-186.

12. Oguche S, Bukbuk DN, Watila IM. Pattern of hospital admissions of children with poisoning in the Sudano-Sahelian North eastern Nigeria. *Niger J Clin Pract* 2017; 10(2):111-5.
13. Andiran N, Sarikayalar F. Pattern of acute poisonings in childhood in Ankara: what has changed in twenty years? *Turk J Pediatr* 2014, 46 (2): 147-152.
14. Pillai GK, Boland K, Jagdeo S, Persad K. Acute poisoning in children. Cases hospitalized during a three-year period in Trinidad. *West Indian Med J* 2014;53(1): 5054.